

Predictive control for bio-protective robotic exoskeletons: closed-loop control of internal body forces

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Abstract—The current exoskeleton and exosuit controllers lack direct control over biological tissue parameters such as muscle force and joint torques. This paper presents a predictive framework for controlling biological Musculotendon Unit (MTU) loads using exoskeletons. It introduces novel closed-form combined human-exoskeleton ordinary differential equation (ODE) models for simulating hopping and walking motions, which are utilized in the nonlinear model Predictive Controller (NMPC) of this framework. Through simulations, the framework demonstrates its capability to maintain MTU force below predefined thresholds. Future work aims to achieve real-time control of MTU load and joint torques during dynamic activities. The proposed framework, with the integration of NMPC, holds promise for enhancing the integration of exoskeleton technology in diverse applications, offering potential improvements in assistive and rehabilitative fields.

I. INTRODUCTION

Creating wearable exosuits and exoskeletons capable of precisely controlling musculotendon unit (MTU) and joint loads in real-time during dynamic activities is challenging. Overcoming this hurdle could significantly reduce injury risks associated with repetitive tasks or high-impact activities, such as walking or labor-intensive industrial work. Furthermore, such technology could enhance the rehabilitation of specific tissues and promote healthy aging by effectively controlling mechanical loads. There were some studies that used MTU loads and joint torques as input to control wearable devices using proportional control [1]–[3]. The aim of most of these studies were to reduce the metabolic cost [1], [2] or to reduce the joint torque or the muscle activity [2], [3].

Current state-of-the-art lower limb exoskeleton controllers lack the capability for direct closed-loop control over biological tissue parameters, such as MTU peak force [4]. Our research aims to bridge this gap by developing a predictive-based control framework designed to control tissue loading in a targeted, assist-as-needed manner, specifically controlling peak Achilles tendon force during cyclic motions. In this paper, we concentrate on the key components of the predictive

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control framework, emphasizing the methodology employed to model the integrated human-exoskeleton system.

II. METHODS

The predictive control framework for controlling MTU loads incorporates several components (Fig. 1), with the Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) algorithm being central. This predictive controller incorporates an internal model, which serves as a constraint in the optimization problem that is solved using the direct collocation numerical method. Complementing the NMPC algorithm, the framework also features an MTU force predictor, which predicts future MTU forces over a pre-specified horizon, and a desired MTU force generator, which sets the target force values for the MTU [5].

Fig. 1. The NMPC control framework. The closed-form dynamics of the combined MTU and motion-related ODE utilizes the pre-determined activation (a) to generate the MTU force in the tendon force predictor (b). The desired tendon force is then estimated using the predicted future MTU force (c) which is then transferred to the NMPC along with the activation and current MTU length and force measured from the human (e).

A. NMPC inner model

To control the MTU force, two sets of closed-form equations are necessary: one for estimating the tendon force and another for relating it to motion [4]. To achieve this, we developed a closed-form equation for tendon force by linearizing the force-velocity relationship of the muscle within a modified damped Hill-type muscle model [6].

In the next step, we formulated an equation for relating the lumped triceps-surae plantarflexors’ forces to the motion of the center of mass (COM) during hopping [5]. Here, we introduce a modified version of this model by adding the ankle rotational motion to the model (Fig. 2-b). This novel model demonstrates greater accuracy in estimating tendon forces and identifying the flight phase during hopping.

By adapting the widely recognized Spring-Loaded Inverted Pendulum (SLIP) model to include a lumped triceps-surae muscles and a rotating ankle, the two modeling approaches used for hopping can be integrated to simulate the behavior of the lumped triceps-surae during walking [7].

Fig. 2. Models used as NMPC inner model and MTU force predictor for hopping (a and b) and walking (c)

B. Prediction

Although MPC is somewhat robust against inaccuracies in activation knowledge [5], predicting the future MTU load requires not only a combined model of the human-exoskeleton system but also a prediction of muscle activation. This approach has been applied to repetitive tasks such as walking and running [8], as well as lifting weights during squat and stoop lifting [9]. The predicted activation is then integrated into the combined model of the human-exoskeleton to determine the future MTU load.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To validate the control framework prior to implementation, the human-exoskeleton system depicted in Fig. 1-e is replaced with a simulated combined human-exoskeleton model. This simulation mimics hopping at various frequencies and muscle excitation amplitudes. Results demonstrate that the NMPC algorithm effectively maintains the MTU

Fig. 3. Performance of the predictive control framework for keeping the MTU force under 3000 N. The dashed lines indicate the active control region

force below a predefined threshold of 3000 N, compared to values approaching 5000 N without assistance.

The dashed line in Figure 3 marks the region where the tendon force predictor anticipates that the MTU force will exceed the threshold in the absence of assistive force, thereby triggering the activation of the controller.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced the structure of a predictive framework for controlling MTU load and discussed various modeling approaches for simulating hopping and walking motions. In the future, this framework will be implemented for real-time control of Achilles MTU load during hopping and walking, as well as for controlling L5-S1 joint load during upper-limb activities [9].

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